

A low cost fractal CPW fed antenna for UWB applications with a circular radiating patch

Akram El Hamdouni¹, Abdelali Tajmouati², Jamal Zbitou³, Hamid Bennis⁴, Ahmed Errkik⁵, Larbi El Abdellaoui⁶, Mohamed Latrach⁷

^{1,2,3,5,6}LMEET Laboratory of Faculty of Sciences and Techniques, Hassan 1st University of Settat, Morocco

⁴TIM Research Team, EST of Meknes, Moulay Ismail University, Morocco

⁷RF-EMC research group, IETR, ESEO, 10 Boulevard Jeanneteau – CS 90717 - 49107 Angers Cedex, France

Article Info

Article history:

Received Mar 13, 2019

Revised Jul 5, 2019

Accepted Jul 23, 2019

Keywords:

CPW

FCC

Fractal geometry

Radiation pattern

Return loss

UWB

ABSTRACT

In this study a validated antenna into simulation and through measurement has been described and analyzed. The coplanar waveguide (CPW) technique has been chosen to feed the radiating patch while the two ground planes have been partially designed in the top side of the substrate. The fractal geometry, applied to the circular radiator, has been obtained by merging the circular and rectangular shapes. The fiberglass FR-4, with a single side of 35µm copper thickness, has been used to achieve the antenna material with a permittivity of 4.4, a thickness of 1.6 mm, a loss tangent of 0.025 and an overall dimension of 34x43 mm². The proposed CPW fractal antenna has been configured to operate in the frequency range 3.1-10.6 GHz published by the federal communications commission (FCC) as an ultra-wide band (UWB). To calculate the return loss, the gain, the current density and the radiation pattern of the simulated antenna, two electromagnetic solvers have been involved which are the CST microwave studio and ADS. The series of measurement have been performed by using the network analyzer and the anechoic chamber in order to confirm the computed antenna.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Akram El Hamdouni,
LMEET Laboratory of Faculty of Sciences and Techniques,
Hassan 1st University of Settat,
Route de Casablanca Km 3.5 BP 539, Morocco.
Email: akram.elhamdouni@yahoo.fr

1. INTRODUCTION

The first definition of the UWB, applied by The Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA) as American standard, has been based on the value of the below Taylor expression $BF = 2(FH - FL)/(FH + FL)$, so the signal is considered as UWB when BF is superior than 0.25. Where BF is the fractional Bandwidth of the signal, FH is the higher frequency and FL is the lower frequency in the spectrum. In February 2002, a new definition of UWB has been published by the Federal communication commission (FCC) as the second American standard, based on the signal bandwidth. So according to the FCC a signal can be known as UWB if it frequency spectrum is similar or greater than 500 MHz [1-5].

In the planar technology, the microstrip feed line remains the most popular technique to establish the microwave transmission due to several advantages, however this method suffers from some limitations mainly belong to the reduced bandwidth offered. Therefore the introduction of the coplanar waveguide

(CPW) technique becomes mandatory in the planar devices and especially in the printed antennas, by depositing the transmission feed line between two narrow ground planes on the top side of the substrate, which offers to the antenna a wider signal spectrum, a less dispersion, low radiation loss, an ease integration with passive and active circuits [6-8]. The Fractal is a rough of an original shape that can be fragmented n times with reduced sizes, this technique offers two important behaviors, the first one is the self-similarity to improve the matching of input impedance in the frequency spectrum, while the second is space filling to increase the miniaturization of the devices [9].

2. ANTENNA GEOMETRY

The CPW technique has been applied to the proposed antenna by designing the transmission line and the ground planes on the top side of the substrate, the radiating patch has been circularly chosen with a fractal geometry obtained by the merging of rectangular and circular shapes by using the Boolean add included in the CST solver as shown in Figure 1. The overall dimensions of the achieved antenna is $43 \times 34 \text{ mm}^2$ which are the dimensions of the FR-4 of Epoxy fiberglass used as substrate with the following features; a thickness of $h=1.6 \text{ mm}$, a permittivity constant $\epsilon_r = 4.4$ and a loss tangent $\tan(\delta) = 0.025$. The entire area of the antenna is $43 \times 34 \text{ mm}^2$. The Figure 2 presents the validated antenna with the different parameters which are optimized by the methods of calculation implemented in the electromagnetic solver. The values are shown in the Table 1. Tables and Figures are presented center, as shown below and cited in the manuscript. The Figure 3 presents the fabricated antenna with the SMA connector soldered simultaneously to the feed line and the two ground planes.

Figure 1. The fragmented shape for the fractal geometry

Figure 2. The geometry of the proposed antenna

Figure 3. The fabricated fractal CPW antenna

Table 1. The calculated and optimized dimensions of the proposed antenna

Parameter	Value (mm)	Comment
L_S	43	Length of antenna
W_S	34	Width of antenna
L_G	16	Length of ground
W_G	15	Width of ground
W_F	3	Width of Feed line
D	17	Diameter of radiator
D_1	9.1	Height of 1 st Circular shape
D_2	6.125	Height of 2 nd Circular shape

3. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The simulation of the achieved antenna has been performed by using two electromagnetic solvers, CST of Microwave Studio, which uses the finite integration technique (FIT) as numerical method, was the main one while the second solver it was ADS which apply the Method of Moment (MoM) [10-17]. The measurement of the proposed CPW antenna in this article has been fulfilled by using the network analyser PNA-X N5247A from agilent technologies and a SMA connector operating until 12 GHz. The return loss has been computed by the two solvers CST and ADS and presented in the Figure 4 with

the measured one, a good agreement between the three graphs appeared in term of input impedance matching in a bandwidth of 120% from 2.99 GHz to 12 GHz which include the FCC band 3.1–10.6 GHz [18-28].

The gain has been calculated in the Figure 5 by using CST only, appears between 1 and 4dB in the lower frequencies, while in higher frequencies the gain reaches the values from 4 to 6dB which means that the validated antenna can be proposed for indoor UWB application in lower frequencies and for outdoor applications in higher frequencies. The current distribution is mainly present in the peripheries between the transmission line and two ground planes in the frequencies 3, 5, 7 and 10 GHz of the FCC band shown respectively in the Figures 6 (a), (b), (c) and (d).

The radiation pattern has been computed by CST in E and H planes for the frequencies 3, 5, 7 and 10 GHz, but has been measured only in H planes in the same frequencies as shown in the Figures 7 (a), (b), (c) and (d). The radiation pattern in E-plane of the simulated antenna is bidirectional in overall frequencies. However in the H-plane the radiations pattern shown unidirectional in the same frequencies into simulation and measurement with some distortions in the measured diagram due to the experience environment.

Figure 4. The S_{11} vs frequency of the CPW antenna by CST and ADS

Figure 5. The gain vs frequency of the CPW antenna

Figure 6. The current density of CPW antenna with slots: (a) @3 GHz, (b) @5 GHz, (c) @7 GHz and (d) @10 GHz

Figure 7. The radiation pattern in E&H-planes by CST and measured in H-plane only:
 (a) @3 GHz, (b) @5 GHz, (c) @7 GHz and (d) @10 GHz

4. CONCLUSION

A novel fractal and CPW fed antenna has been validated into simulation and by manufacturing in order to operate in the UWB. So, the structure has been computed and optimized by using two electromagnetic solvers ADS and CST-MW. The simulated parameters present an important result, in terms of return loss, gain, current distribution and radiation pattern, in the FCC frequency range 3.1–10.6 GHz with a bandwidth of 120%. A good agreement between the computed and measured parameters has been appeared which permit to achieve a printed antenna with an acceptable performances, a low cost, a low profile and an ease integration with passive and active circuits.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. F. Morabito and P. Rocca, "Reducing the number of elements in phase-only reconfigurable arrays generating sum and difference patterns," *IEEE Antennas and Wireless Propagation Letters*, vol. 14, pp. 1338-1341, 2015.
- [2] N. M. Sahar, et al., "Analysis of Fractal Antenna for Ultra-Wideband Applicatio," *Research Journal of Applied Sciences, Engineering and Technology*, vol. 7, no. 10, pp. 2022-2026, 2014.
- [3] M. Levy, et al., "A novel fractal uwb antenna for earthquake and tsunami prediction application (LETPA)," *IEEE Canadian Conference of Electrical and Computer Engineering (CCECE)*, 2013.
- [4] B. R. Rao, et al., "Design of Circular with triangle Microstrip Fractal Antenna for Dual band and UWB applications," *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*, vol. 4, no. 7, pp. 1203-1206, Jul 2013.
- [5] H. M. AlSabbagh, et al., "A UWB Fractal Antenna for Body Area Network Applications," *2012 Loughborough Antennas and Propagation Conference 12-13 November 2012*, Loughborough, UK, 2012.
- [6] H. L. Lee, et al., "Broadband planar antenna having round corner rectangular wide slot," *IEEE Antennas and Propagation Society International Symposium 2002*, Jun 2002.
- [7] R. L. Yadava, et al., "Multiband Triangular Fractal Antenna for Mobile Communications," *International Journal of Engineering Science and Technology*, vol. 2, no. 11, pp. 6335-6348, 2010.
- [8] S. Qu and C. Ruan, "Quadrat bowtie antenna with round corners," *IEEE International Conference on Ultra-Wideband. 205 (ICU 2005)*, Sep 2005.

- [9] M. K. A. Rahim, et al., "Wideband Sierpinski Carpet Monopole Antenna," *Proceedings of Asia-Pacific Conference on Applied Electromagnetics, Malaysia*, pp. 62-65, 2005.
- [10] D. H. Werner and S. Ganguly, "An Overview of Fractal Antenna Engineering Research," *IEEE Antennas and Propagation Magazine*, vol. 45, no. 1, pp. 38-57, 2003.
- [11] Z. N. Low, et al., "Low-Cost PCB Antenna for UWB Applications," *IEEE antennas and wireless propagation letters*, vol. 4, pp. 237-239, 2005.
- [12] T. Yang, et al., "Small, Planar Ultra-Wideband Antennas with Top-Loading," *IEEE Antennas and Propagation Society International Symposium 2005*, Jul 2005.
- [13] M. Al Hussein, et al., "Design of a Compact and Low-Cost Fractal-Based UWB PCB Antenna," *2009 National Radio Science Conference*, 2009.
- [14] R. Kumar and S. Gaikwad, "On the Design of Nano - arm Fractal Antenna for UWB Wireless Applications," *Journal of Microwaves Optoelectronics and Electromagnetic Applications*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 158-171, Jun 2013.
- [15] N. Kushwaha and R. Kumar, "An uwb fractal antenna with defected ground structure and swastika shape electromagnetic band gap," *Progress in Electromagnetics Research B*, vol. 52, no. 52, pp. 383-403, 2013.
- [16] Kumar and K. P. Ray, "Broadband Microstrip Antennas," Artech House, 685 Canton Street Norwood, pp. 7-20 2003.
- [17] T. Isernia and A. F. Morabito, "Mask-constrained power synthesis of linear arrays with even excitations," *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 64, no. 7, pp. 3212-3217, 2016.
- [18] A. El Hamdouni, et al., "A New Design of an UWB Circular Fractal Printed Antenna," *TELKOMNIKA Telecommunication Computing Electronics and Control*, vol. 16, no. 5, pp. 1931-1938, Oct 2018.
- [19] S. Elajoumi, et al., "Bandwidth enhancement of compact microstrip rectangular antennas for UWB applications," *TELKOMNIKA Telecommunication Computing Electronics and Control*, vol. 17, no. 3, pp. 1559-1568, Jun 2019.
- [20] D. H. Werner and S. Ganguly. "An Overview of Fractal Antenna Engineering Research," *IEEE Antennas and Propagation Magazine*, vol. 45, no. 1, pp. 38-57, February 2003.
- [21] Z. N. Low, J. H. Cheong, and C. L. Law. "Low-Cost PCB Antenna for UWB Applications," *IEEE antennas and wireless propagation letters*, vol. 4, pp. 237-239, 2005.
- [22] T. Yang, W.A. Davis, and W.L. Stutzman. "Small, Planar. Ultra-Wideband Antennas with Top-Loading," *IEEE Antennas and Propagation Society International Symposium 2005*, July 2005.
- [23] M. Al Hussein, A. Ramadan, A. El Hajj and K. Kabalan, "Design of a Compact and Low-Cost Fractal-Based UWB PCB Antenna," *International Conference: Sciences of Electronic, Technologies of Information and Telecommunications*, 2009.
- [24] R. Kumar and S. Gaikwad. "On the Design of Nano-arm Fractal Antenna for UWB Wireless Applications", *Journal of Microwaves Optoelectronics and Electromagnetic Applications*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 158-171, June 2013.
- [25] N. Kushwaha, and R. Kumar. "An Uwb Fractal Antenna with Defected Ground Structure and Swastika Shape Elec-Tromagnetic Band Gap", *Progress in Electromagnetics Research B*, vol. 52, no. 52, pp. 383-403, 2013.
- [26] Kumar and K. P. Ray, "Broadband Microstrip Antennas," Artech House, 685 Canton Street Norwood, pp. 7-20, 2003.
- [27] T. Isernia and A. F. Morabito, "Mask-constrained power synthesis of linear arrays with even excitations", *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 64, no. 7, pp. 3212-3217, 2016.
- [28] A. F. Morabito, and P. Rocca, "Reducing the number of elements in phase-only reconfigurable arrays generating sum and difference patterns", *IEEE Antennas and Wireless Propagation Letters*, vol. 14, pp. 1338-1341, 2015.